

Does The Coupling Constant Series Vary Overtime? 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series in the first and second representation, analysis of the varying overtime can be made. From the first representation, net curvature, a varying value of the coupling constants is possible. On the other hand, analysis according to spin makes it more complicated, and seems to indicate that it will not be possible, as than the result will be particles with have non-integer or half integer spins.

Introduction

The new coupling series has several representations. The first is net curvature of discrete amount on the matric tensor, on a varying Lorentz manifold with (3,1) signature. The discrete amounts of curvature comes to an agreement with Planck constant. In the 8T the photon is associated with $N_V = (+5)$ units of net curvature. Equations (1.31) and (1.33) represent the net curvature representation.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.3)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.31)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.32)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.33)$$

From that representation we were able to show that the net curvature can vary overtime, that is how we created the duality of the first three interactions at 24 + 2 variations. From that point of view, at certain instances the coupling magnitudes can vary overtime. The change in the coupling is due to the net curvature, or the bosonic propagation variation.

Another way to analyze it is by using the matric tensor. Each boson is a ripple on the manifold. The ripple has certain spin; the result is a curvature vortex on the matric tensor. Overtime the ripple distributed over larger and larger areas of the matric tensor. As a result, it gets more and more flat as it covers more area, and therefore weaker and weaker, there could be slight variation in the coupling term over long periods.

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \quad (1.33)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \quad (1.34)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1 \quad (1.35)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.36)$$

Equations (1.33) to (1.35) are the spin representations. Equation (1.36) is the result. Slight variations in the net variation than means bosons with spin which is less or more than one as the net variation will not be on the prime critical line. We can regard the bosons to be net curvature of closed shape as they are generated by the same element, i.e. the invariant (3) from the second term and above.

$$(e) = (3) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(5)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.37)$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(\gamma)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.38)$$

Such a construction is than against observation as no particles with such spins where ever found or even theorized as far as one knows. From the spin representation alone, variations in the coupling terms is not very likable. Another point, if slight variations were allowed than the result would be a set of plank constants, not just one value. That is to say that there are certain values that can be emitted or absorbed from fermions. As far as we know today, there is only one plank constant. Overall, two points of analysis, from curvature viewpoint and ripples across the manifold, it is possible. From spin analysis, it is not.

The author regards it to be an open question. However, his intuition tells him that in that case, the spin representation is stronger and thus there should not be variation overtime.

References

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- [3] O. Manor. "The Planck Constant and Prime Curvatures" In: (2021)